

KEY INDICATORS

The organic sector holds a prominent position within Austria's agricultural industry. Austria is the only EU country to already exceed the EU target of 25% (on average) of agricultural land under organic management, reaching more than 700 kha (27.5%) in 2022. This represents a 54% growth compared with 2001. Austria is also among the top countries regarding organic market share reaching a retail sales value of 2.5 M€ or 11.6% of the total national food market in 2022, up more than 1000% compared with 2001. These developments built on organic policy support already since 1992, including the environmental programme ÖPUL, as well as high consumer demand for organic products and increased producer prices since 2017. Organic retail sales rely on the broad availability of organic products in highly concentrated retail chains. After numerous food scandals in the 1990s, private and public trademark programmes were established to build consumer confidence and trust in the organic sector.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2022

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

459,326 ha (15.7%)

705,835 ha (27.5%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2022

53.7%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2022

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

78,072 ha (5.9%)

290,746 ha (22%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

2,284 ha (2.8%)

15,214 ha (22.4%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

326,239 ha (22.4%)

399,814 ha (31.8%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

239 † (5.3%) (2021)

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2022

Producers (Share of Total)

18,290 (11.6%)

26,251 (23.7%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

41

Processors

573

2,374

Importers

30

86

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2022

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

225 M €

2,496 M€ (11.5%)

Per Capita Consumption

28.1 €

274 €

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2022

1,009 %

Imports

N/D

51,097 †

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

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DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN AUSTRIA

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey, based on BMLRT, Eurostat and Nic Lampkin

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC RETAIL SALES IN AUSTRIA

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on AMA Marketing and further sources

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Austrian CAP strategic plan provides for modest increases in organic area supported and expenditure, with more environmental requirements being added to the organic support scheme, while payment rates for arable and horticulture are reduced. The 23% of UAA planned to be supported in 2027 contrasts with the 27.5% certified organic in 2022, and the 35% targeted for 2030. Additional costs during conversion are not compensated.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

	2018	2027
Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	515 kha	610 kha (+18%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	19.4%	23% (+18%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	80.6%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	121 M€	154 M€ (+27%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	234 €	252 € (+7%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	753 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	500 M€	
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	2,362 M€	26.3%
Total CAP Expenditure	8,650 M€	8.7%

*Including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	70-225	70-230	450-1000	700	700
	2023	P2	70-215	205-325	305-405	500-700	700
Change from 2019 to 2023			0%	-10%	-40%	0%	0%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	70-225	70-230	450-1000	700	700
	2023	P2	70-215	205-325	305-405	500-700	700
Change from 2019 to 2023			0%	-10%	-40%	0%	0%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2023		0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Austria has had a series of organic action plans starting in 2001. The latest (the sixth) Austrian national OAP contains more market-related actions than previously, with a corresponding emphasis on improving market, financial and statistical information, and strengthening promotion of organic farming benefits to consumers.

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2015-22	20% of UAA by 2016, more by 2020	100% of organic products sold as organic by 2022
Current Action Plan	2023-30	30% of UAA by 2027, 35% by 2030	22% of canteen food by 2023, 55% by 2030

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (2015 - 2022)

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2023 - 2030)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Austria is just over 5%. Organic aquaculture has been supported as part of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture, including investment aids and consumer information. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

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